

HIGHLY EFFICIENT FAST ARCHITECTURES FOR DISCRETE WAVELET TRANSFORMS BASED ON THEIR FLOWGRAPH REPRESENTATION

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ABSTRACT

Flowgraph representation of discrete wavelet transforms (DWTs) is presented which can be considered as a new alternative definition of wavelets. It is shown that this representation is useful for developing efficient algorithms and VLSI architectures. As an examples two DWT architectures are proposed with the efficiency (counted as the measure of the average utilization of PEs) of approximately 100%. Proposed architectures are very fast and provide excellent performance with respect to area-time characteristics (see Table 1). They are scalable, simple, regular, and free of long connections (depending on the length of input signal). Results can be easily extended to inverse DWTs as well.

1 Introduction

In the last decade, the Discrete Wavelet Transforms (DWTs) have been intensively studied and successfully applied to a wide range of applications: numerical analysis, biomedicine, different branches of image and video processing, signal processing techniques, speech compression/decompression, etc. They have often been found preferable to other traditional transform techniques since they offer useful features such as: inherent scalability, linear computational complexity, low aliasing distortion for signal processing applications, and adaptive time-frequency windows.

In most of the applications, real-time implementation of DWTs is required in order to achieve attractive results. Therefore, the implementation of the DWT by means of dedicated VLSI ASIC's has recently captivated the attention of a number of researchers, and many DWT architectures have already been proposed [1]-[8]. Some of these devices have been targeted to have a low hardware complexity but they require at least $2N$ clock cycles (cc's) to compute the DWT of a sequence of length N [1]-[3]. Nevertheless, also a large number of devices, having a period of approximately N cc's, has been designed [2]-[6]. Most of these architectures exploit the Recursive Pyramid Algorithm (RPA) [9] based on the tree-structured filter bank representation of DWTs (see Fig. 1). In this representation the input signal

is processed by several stages of decomposition where the length of the processed signal is twice reduced from a stage to stage. Even though, pipelining has been employed to implement this structure, however, known pipelined architectures use the same number of processing elements for every pipeline stage. Balancing of the pipeline stages is achieved by making the clocking frequency twice smaller from a stage to stage. As a result of under-utilization of processing elements, the typical efficiency parameter for known architectures is estimated in much less than 100%. Highly (about 100%) efficient architectures have been developed in [10, 11] by including approximately twice lower number of processing elements from a stage to stage.

In this paper we propose a new approach for DWT implementation based on representation of DWTs using flowgraphs similar to those widely used for traditional fast transforms like the fast Fourier, Walsh, Haar and other transforms (see [12]). Although the flowgraph representation has been found very useful in designing implementations of traditional fast transforms and even though relations of DWTs and traditional fast transform algorithms are well known, however, the flowgraph representation of DWTs has yet not been (in our best knowledge) described and employed for designing pipelined DWT architectures. In the next section we shortly give the flowgraph representation of DWTs which is, essentially, an alternative definition of DWTs. There is no computational redundancy in the flowgraph representation of DWTs unlike the tree-structured filter bank representation where computational redundancy is reflected by downsampling and a special care should be made to avoid this redundancy. The flowgraph representation is also rather demonstrative, easy-to-understand and regular, which provides a systematic approach to designing the DWT implementations. As example of such designs we present two architectures (called FPP DWT and LPP DWT) in Section 3. The efficiency of both architectures is approximately 100%. They are very fast and provide excellent performance with respect to area-time characteristics (see Table 1). They are scalable, simple, regular, and free of long connections (de-

Figure 1: Tree structured filter bank representation of DWTs

pending on the length of input signal). Presented results can be easily extended to inverse DWTs as well.

2 The flowgraph representation of DWTs

There are several alternative definitions of DWTs. Most of the existing DWT architectures are based on the tree-structured filter bank representation of DWTs (see Fig. 1) where several stages of signal decomposition are applied. Every stage consists of low-pass and high-pass filtering followed by downsampling by 2 of the results of both bands. Another widespread definition of DWTs is based on the matrix approach. The scheme on Fig. 1 is equivalent to the discrete linear transform $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{H} \cdot \mathbf{x}$, where $\mathbf{x}$ and $\mathbf{y}$ are the input and the output vectors of size $N = 2^m$, and $\mathbf{H}$ is the DWT matrix of order $N \times N$ which is formed as the product of sparse matrices

$$\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{H}^{(J)} \mathbf{H}^{(J-1)} \dots \mathbf{H}^{(1)}, \quad 1 \leq J \leq m;$$

$$\mathbf{H}^{(j)} = \begin{pmatrix} D_j & 0 \\ 0 & I_{2^m - 2^{m-j+1}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad j = 1, \dots, m, \quad (1)$$

where D_j is the analysis $2^{m-j+1} \times 2^{m-j+1}$ matrix at stage j , and I_k is the identity $k \times k$ matrix ($k = 2^m - 2^{m-j+1}$). If the vector of coefficients of the low-pass and of the high-pass filters in the scheme on Fig. 1 are respectively denoted as $LP = [l_1, \dots, l_L]$, and $HP = [h_1, \dots, h_L]$, (L being the length of the filters) then the matrix D_j is of the form:

$$D_j = \begin{pmatrix} l_1 & l_2 & \dots & l_L & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & l_1 & l_2 & \dots & l_L & \dots & 0 \\ & & & \ddots & & & & \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & & \dots & l_1 & l_2 \\ h_1 & h_2 & \dots & h_L & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & h_1 & h_2 & \dots & h_L & \dots & 0 \\ & & & \ddots & & & & \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & & \dots & h_1 & h_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$= P_j \cdot \begin{pmatrix} l_1 & l_2 & \dots & l_L & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ h_1 & h_2 & \dots & h_L & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & l_1 & l_2 & \dots & l_L & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & h_1 & h_2 & \dots & h_L & \dots & 0 \\ & & & \ddots & & & & \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & & \dots & l_1 & l_2 \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & & \dots & h_1 & h_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where P_j is the matrix of the perfect unshuffle operator (see [12]) of the size $2^{m-j+1} \times 2^{m-j+1}$.

Adopting the representation (1)-(2) the DWT is computed in J stages (J being the resolution level):

$$\mathbf{x}^0 = \mathbf{x}; \quad \mathbf{x}^j = \mathbf{H}^{(j)} \mathbf{x}^{j-1}, \quad j = 1, \dots, J; \quad \mathbf{y} = \mathbf{x}^J. \quad (3)$$

Computation of (3) with the matrices $\mathbf{H}^{(j)}$ of (1), (2) can be clearly demonstrated using a flowgraph representation. An example for the case $N = 2^3 = 8$, $L = 4$ and $J = 3$ is shown in Fig. 2. The flowgraph consists of J stages, the j th stage $j = 1, \dots, J$, having 2^{m-j} nodes, each node (depicted as boxes on Fig. 2) representing the basic DWT operation (see Fig. 2(b)). Every node has L incoming edges from the consecutive nodes of the preceding stage (or, for the nodes of the first stage from inputs) and two outgoing edges. An upper (lower) outgoing edge represents the value of the inner product of the vector of low-pass (high-pass) filter coefficients with the vector of the values of incoming edges. Outgoing values of a stage are permuted according to the perfect unshuffle operator so that all the low-pass components (the values of upper outgoing edges) are collected in the first half and the high-pass components are collected at the second half. Low-pass components are then used as input to the following stage or (for the nodes of the last stage) represent output values¹. High-pass components represent output values at a given resolution.

Essentially, the flowgraph representation gives an alternative, rather demonstrative and easy-to-understand definition of discrete wavelets. In this definition there is no computational redundancy inherent to the tree-structured filter bank representation (which can be seen from downsampling). Therefore, it is very convenient for analyzing and implementing the discrete wavelets. This definition also clearly demonstrates the relations between DWTs and traditional fast transforms. For example, for $L = 2$ the DWT flowgraph defines a subclass of the family of Haar-like transforms studied in [13].

3 Highly efficient scalable DWT architectures

The DWT flowgraph described in the previous section is very regular and provides a systematic approach to design different parallel DWT algorithms and architectures similar to as the well known fast transform flowgraphs provided for the traditional transforms [12]. Below, due to the lack of the space, we present only two examples of how DWT architectures can be obtained

¹Here we consider only Haar-wavelet transforms. An extension to Walsh-wavelet and wavelet packet transforms is quite apparent

Figure 2: (a) The DWT flowgraph ($N = 8, L = 6, J = 3$); (b) operation of the node (the basic DWT operation)

Figure 3: A possible structure for PEs

by analyzing the flowgraph. In fact, these architectures can be considered as extensions of the parallel-pipelined designs proposed in [13] for the family of Haar-like transforms.

3.1 The fully parallel-pipelined (FPP) architecture

This architecture, which we call FPP, is straightforwardly obtained by directly "one-to-one" mapping the DWT flowgraph to the processor architecture where edges of the flowgraph represent interconnections and the nodes represent processor elements (PEs). Different structures of PEs implementing the basic DWT operation can be developed. An example is the PE consisting of two columns of multipliers and two trees of adders as shown in Fig. 3 where pipelined multipliers and adders can be used². The input to the FPP can be made as word-parallel (consider small circles at the first stage on Fig. 2(a) as input ports) as well as word-serial by adding a shift register at the input and making use of buffering.

The architecture can be efficiently pipelined (consider small circles at intermediate stages on Fig. 2(a) as latches). In this case, we assume DWTs of a stream of vector-signals (of length N) input to the architecture (suppose, e.g. a separable 2-D transform) at the rate of one vector-signal per one time unit where the duration of the time is assumed to be the period of one multiplication (which is, in the pipelined mode, the time needed for one basic DWT operation). It is easy to see that approximately 100% efficiency (counted as the measure of the average utilization of PEs) is achieved in the pipelined mode. It should be noted that a close efficiency is reached only in the two designs of [10, 11], whereas other known pipelined DWT architectures reach much less than 100% average efficiency. It

²This structure can be further simplified by making use of dependencies between low-pass and high-pass filter coefficients

also should be noted that the architecture is very regular and needs an easy control. It does not contain long connections depending on the size of the input but only connections of the maximum of $O(L)$ length.

Table 1 summarizes Area-Time characteristics of the architecture (both in pipelined and non-pipelined modes) in comparison with some known DWT architectures. These characteristics have been obtained under the assumption that the area unit is the one occupied by one adder and one multiplier, and the time unit is (as above) the time for one multiplication and one addition. The same assumption is normally done for performance evaluation of DWT architectures by other authors. Note that the proposed design provides constant time (on the average per one vector-signal) period implementation of DWTs whereas other architectures require at least $O(N)$ time period. This results in a very high performance with respect to the AT_p^2 parameter. However, FPP requires a large area which makes it impractical for processing long input signals. A more sophisticated architecture is considered in the next section.

3.2 The scalable limited parallel-pipelined (LPP) architecture

This architecture, which we call LPP, is essentially obtained by decomposing the DWT of a long signal of length N into a stream of shorter DWTs of length 2^J (in the most of applications $J \ll \log_2 N$). With a slight modification, the previous architecture can be used to process this stream of vectors in the pipelined mode. The case of $L = 6$ and $J = 3$ is depicted in Fig. 4. At the first step, the vector $[x_0, \dots, x_7]$ enters into the input registers. At the second stage the vector $[x_8, \dots, x_{15}]$ enters into the input registers so that the components $x_0, \dots, x_7, x_8, x_9$ begin to be processed with the PEs of the first group. At the next step the vector $[x_{16}, \dots, x_{23}]$ enters into the input registers and the values of $x_8, \dots, x_{15}, x_{16}, x_{17}$ enter into the first group of PEs. Computation then proceeds in a similar way.

Among the useful features of the architecture, let us note its regularity, easy control, absence of long (depending on N) connections and actually independence of the architecture on N meaning that DWTs of different length can be computed with the same hardware. It is easy to note that LPP, as well as FPP, operates at approximately full (100%) efficiency. Input to the device can be made as word-parallel as well as word-serial. Ta-

Table 1: Comparative performance of some DWT architectures

Architectures	Area, A	Period, T_p	AT_p^2
FPP (non-pipelined)	$2NL(1 - 1/2^J)$	$J \lceil \log_2 L \rceil$	$2NLJ^2 \lceil \log_2 L \rceil^2 (1 - 1/2^J)$
FPP DWT (pipelined)	$2NL(1 - 1/2^J)$	1 (per vector)	$2NL(1 - 1/2^J)$
LPP DWT	$2^J - 1(2L - 1)$	$\approx N/2^J$	$\approx N^2L/2^{J-1}$
Architectures of [10,11]	$4L$ or $\sum_{j=1}^J \lceil L/2^{j-2} \rceil$	$N/2$	$\approx N^2L$
Architectures in [2-6]	$2L$	N	$2N^2L$
Architectures in [2, 3]	L	$2N$	$4N^2L$
Architectures in [1, 7]	JL	N	N^2JL

 Figure 4: The LPP DWT architecture ($L = 6, J = 3$)

Table 1 demonstrates excellent Area-Time characteristics of the proposed architecture.

4 Conclusion

Two architectures for discrete wavelet transforms have been proposed based on their flowgraph representation. The efficiency of both architectures, counted as the measure of the average utilization of PEs, is approximately 100%. Both architectures are very fast and provide excellent performance with respect to area-time characteristics (see Table 1). They are scalable, simple, regular, and free of long connections (depending on the length of input signal).

References

- [1] S. B. Pan, and R. H. Park, "New Systolic Arrays for Computation of the 1-D Discrete Wavelet Transform," Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing, 1997, Vol. 5, 1997, pp. 4113-4116.
- [2] M. Vishwanath, R. M. Owens, and M. J. Irwin, "VLSI Architectures for the Discrete Wavelet Transform," IEEE Trans. on Circ. and Syst. II: Analog and Digital Signal Processing, vol. 42, n. 5, May 1995, pp.305-316.
- [3] J. Fridman, and S. Manolakos, "Discrete Wavelet Transform: Data Dependence Analysis and Synthesis of Distributed Memory and Control Array Architectures," IEEE Trans. on Signal Proc., vol. 45, n. 5, May 1997, pp. 1291-1308.
- [4] T. C. Denk, and K. K. Parhi, "Systolic VLSI Architectures for 1-D Discrete Wavelet Transform," Proceedings of the Thirty-Second Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems & Computers, 1998, vol. 2, pp. 1220-1224.
- [5] G. Knowles, "VLSI Architecture for the Discrete Wavelet Transform," El. Letters, vol.26, n. 15, 1990, pp. 1184-85.
- [6] C. Chakrabarti, M. Vishwanath, and R. M. Owens, "Architectures for Wavelet Transforms: A Survey," Journal of VLSI Signal Processing, vol. 14, n. 2, 1996, pp. 171-192.
- [7] S. B. Syed, M. A. Bayoumi, "A Scalable Architecture for Discrete Wavelet Transform," Proceedings of Computer Architectures for Machine Perception (CAMP '95), 1995, pp. 44 -50.
- [8] F. Marino, "A 'Double-Face' Bit-Serial Architecture for the 1-D Discrete Wavelet Transform", *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems II - Analog and Digital Signal Processing*, vol. 47, No 1, Jan., 2000, pp. 65-71.
- [9] M. Vishwanath, "The Recursive Pyramid Algorithm for the Discrete Wavelet Transform," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 42, n. 3, 1994, pp. 673-677.
- [10] F. Marino, D. Gevorkian, J. Astola, "Highly efficient High-Speed/Low-Power Architectures for the 1-D DWT," submitted to *IEEE Trans. on Circuits and Systems II*.
- [11] F. Marino, D. Gevorkian, J. Astola, "High-Speed/Low-Power 1-D DWT Architectures with high efficiency," to appear in *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Circuits and Systems*, May 28-31, Geneva, Switzerland.
- [12] D.Z. Gevorkian, *Computational Aspects of Discrete Linear Transforms and Rank Order Based Filters*, Thesis for the degree of Doctor of Technology, May 1997, 214 pages.
- [13] J.T. Astola, S.S. Aghaian, and D.Z. Gevorkian, "Parallel algorithms and architectures for a family of Haar-like transforms," in *Proceedings of SPIE's International Symposium on Electronic Imaging: Science and Technology*, **2421**, Feb., 1995, San Jose, California, USA.